

1 **ER organellar function during TE commitment.**

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6 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
7 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We observed important changes in
8 ER organellar function including that of OS9 in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

9 Citations

10 1. Seaayfan, E., Defontaine, N., Demaretz, S., Zaarour, N. and Laghmani, K., 2016. OS9 protein
11 interacts with Na-K-2Cl Co-transporter (NKCC2) and targets its immature form for the endoplasmic
12 reticulum-associated degradation pathway. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 291(9), pp.4487-4502.